

PHYSIOLOGICAL BENEFITS OF RESISTANCE TRAINING IN DEPRESSIVE PERSONS: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT The current society, due to the technological advance, excessive collections, reigning individualism, among others, is faced with a significant increase of individuals with depression. Some authors conceptualize depression as a disease where the individual feels inferior to everything and everyone, with no capacity and willingness to face the challenges, because it presents a feeling of fear of failure, thus promoting a reduction of the sense of pleasure, irritability, feelings of guilt and, in more severe cases, suicidal thoughts. The concept of depression is applied to a mood disorder, encompassing cognitive, behavioral, physiological, social, economic and religious factors, since depression is considered an evil that is rooted in the individual's "I" interfering in a negative way the course of their thoughts and decisions. In addition to these characteristic feelings of depression, one study points out that depression also generates disorders at the brain level, due to the dysregulation of essential neurotransmitters, as well as the reduction of cognitive function, which promotes the formulation and decision of an adequate response front to a stressor event. Resistance training, which presents a voluntary action of the skeletal muscle against a resistance, through stimuli, promoting metabolic stress and developing different types of strength in the individual, from neuromuscular and hormonal adaptations and cognitive function, when associated to an organized training program, considering questions related to the load, volume, order and interval of the exercises. Therefore, with this literature review, we see the importance of including resistance training to the treatment of depression, since regular and long-term exercises promote hormonal and cognitive benefits, helping and improving the individual's ability to generate responses to the stressor event, developing self-confidence.

KEYWORDS depression, resistance training, force, mood disorder, physiological benefits, physical exercises

INTRODUCTION

From the beginnings of society, one realises that the individual is surrounded by different feelings, giving prominence to feelings of hopelessness, apathy, indifference, diminished pleasure, since they are feelings characteristic of depression. It is possible

to say, then, that depression and the attempt to understand it was already issued in the life of the individual since Antiquity (PARANHOS & WERLANG, 2009), since they could be only the natural feelings of the human being, or still be a result of an imbalance of the organism, in other words, a disease. Moreover, even with technological and scientific advancement over the years, society has been unable to determine the symptoms and components that can effectively claim the diagnosis of depressive symptoms.

According to COSTA (2010), one of the fastest growing diseases in the population today is depression. This high level of depressive illness in recent years can be translated through some studies in the field of general medicine, which suggests a 3-10-fold increase in the occurrence of this disease, which shows a redistribution by age and gender, since the depression

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already reaches an age range between 15-44 years, maintaining a prevalence in women (10-25%), whereas in men this incidence is lower, 5-12% (PARANHOS & WERLANG, 2009). According to data from the WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION (2001), depression is considered the main disability factor measured by the Years of Life Lost, due to premature deaths and the fourth leading cause of morbidity and loss of quality of life measured by Years of Adjusted Life Inability. The World Health Organization's projection is that these numbers be increased by 2020, reaching all ages and both sexes, and it is even predicted that depression can be seen as the evil of the 21st century (PERES, 2006 apud PARANHOS & WERLANG, 2009), because BOTEGA et al. (2006) present data that every 20 individuals, one is hit by a depressive episode during their life, and every 50 diagnoses, one presents the need for hospitalization and 15% commit suicide.

From these data, it is seen that depression is a disease considered a severe public health problem, since it generates high social costs and the continuous risk of suicide (HEXSEL, 2004), besides the fact that the depressive individual has their personal and social lives are considerably affected, for example, these individuals use medical services more often, they present a reduction in their productivity at work and their quality of life, mainly when associated with chronic diseases (Fleck et al. 2002). These attitudes of the depressed individual are due to the fact that this individual presents a subjective feeling of sadness, for example DEL PORTO (1999) describes this sensation from the reduction of the capacity to feel pleasure by the activities in general and the interest in the environment; other authors still claim that the depressive individual presents with psychomotor alterations, referring to a process of psychomotor retardation or retardation, or, according to DELOYA (2002), depression is characterized as a state in which the individual considers himself incapable of finding ways to deal with the new demands of contemporary society through reigning individualism, excessive collections of competence in work, technological advancement and / or unemployment, reaffirming the analysis given by COSTA (2010), where depression is seen as a growing disease in today's society, mainly because of this technological expansion, requiring excessive speed and skills of individuals, overloading them with duties and obligations and limiting their moments of pleasure, distractions, affective relationships, among others.

Aiming to reverse this expansive picture in which depression is found, significant importance is attached to the practice of physical exercise, for example. In other words, it is seen that the habit of practising physical exercises is beneficial not only concerning the physical, but also to the social and the psychological of the active individual. In relation to the psychological and social benefits generated by the regular practice of physical exercises, CHEIK et. al. (2003) affirm that through physical exercise the individual develops a greater social participation, increasing biopsicofísico well-being, besides collaborating for an increase or maintenance of the levels of endorphin and dopamine released by the organism during the exercise and these hormones provide to the individual a state of tranquility and post-effort analgesic (relaxing) effect, allowing this individual a psychosocial balance in the face of stressful events. In addition to providing an improvement in cognitive function, as several studies suggest that active individuals present a lower risk in the development of mental illness (ANTUNES et al., 2006). However, for these benefits to be effective in the individual, it is necessary to include a training program in their routine (adherence to the practice of physical exercise), as in the case of resistance training,

which consists of a voluntary action of the skeletal muscle against a resistance, through stimuli, promoting metabolic stress and developing different types of strength in the individual, through neuromuscular and hormonal adjustments (FERREIRA et al., 2013). In other words, some studies conducted in the USA suggest that the controlled and organized practice of physical exercise offers a reduction in the symptoms of depression and anxiety for the general population (Melo et al., 2005).

ANTUNES et. al. (2006) emphasize that this training method results in improvement in the cerebral circulation, causing alterations in the synthesis and degradation of neurotransmitters, since its practice causes cerebral blood flow to be increased, as well as to increase the release of several neurotransmitters and concentrations of serotonin, popularly called as pleasure hormone. Predicting these benefits promoted by training and aiming the association of resistance training in individuals with depression, it is necessary to determine how these reductions of mood disorders after exercise, through a bibliographic review, seeking a better understanding of the symptoms and changes that depression causes in the body and on resistance training, including hormonal, neural and physiological adaptations. To analyze the physiological benefits of resistance training in depressed people.

LITERATURE REVIEW

RESISTANCE TRAINING

Resistance training, also called strength training, according to WINETTI et al. (2001), is a training method that involves the voluntary action of the skeletal muscle against some external form of resistance, provided by the body, free weights or machines. In this same line of thought, SANTARÉM (1999) apud MODESTO & SOUSA (2012), defines resistance training as a form of physical preparation, with the use of weights as a form of resistance against muscular actions, where strength is the main valence trained (GUEDES et al., 2008).

For FERREIRA et al. (2013), resistance training is the voluntary action of skeletal muscle against resistance, through stimuli, promoting metabolic stress and developing different types of strength in the individual, through neuromuscular and hormonal adaptations.

According to COSTA (2004) apud HAWERROTH et al. (2010), the benefits of resistance training go well beyond aesthetics, being beneficial for reducing stress, increasing social interaction, decreasing sedentary lifestyle, and avoiding and controlling some pathologies. Resistance training also includes cardiorespiratory benefits, decreases the risk of chronic degenerative diseases, and improves cognitive function, i.e. physically active individuals, have a lower risk of suffering from mental disorders than sedentary individuals (ANTUNES et al. al., 2006).

As PRADA et al. (2009), during the training session (resistance training), the body is required to use two metabolic pathways, whose function is to supply the energy required for the exercise. One of these pathways is known as the allelic anaerobic pathway, lasting more or less 10 seconds, using ATP and CP (creatine phosphate) as the initial source of energy, more specifically, ATP is degraded in ADP (adenosine diphosphate) + P, then the CP is broken generating energy for the organism and the remaining P is associated with ADP forming a new molecule of ATP (it takes about 3 to 5 minutes). Then the other route, called the lactic anaerobic route, is used, whose function is to use glycogen as an energetic substrate, which is chemically disintegrated, producing the lactic acid, transported to the blood,

where from a buffer it forms the lactate (recovery takes around 5 to 24 hours).

About the benefits generated by resistance training, AN-TUNES et al. (2006) emphasize the improvement in cerebral circulation and alteration in the synthesis and degradation of neurotransmitters, since its practice causes cerebral blood flow to be increased, as well as increase the release of several neurotransmitters and serotonin concentrations. In addition to these benefits generated by resistance training, ZANETTI et al. (2013) emphasize that during the training session, there is an increase in blood flow to the muscles involved in a given exercise, increasing the supply of oxygen and nutrients, and decreasing metabolic dross, such as carbon dioxide, lactate and ions hydrogen, therefore, the cardiovascular system suffers the influence of neural and metabolic stimuli, due to the need to increase its activity.

Another benefit of resistance training is its ability to generate force, which is needed in all movements. According to RATAMESS et al. (2009), the generation of force depends on the activation of the motor units recruited according to the exercise limit, first activating the slow units and then the fast units, that is, the generation of force occurs through numerous neuromuscular mechanisms, characterized by increase in muscle strength in the first weeks of training and its manifestation occurs in the long term due to an improvement in neural function, such as an increase in the cross-sectional area of the muscle fiber (positively related to maximal force production), changes in muscular architecture and adaptations and increase of metabolites such as H⁺ for resistance. Still according to RATAMESS et al. (2009), the benefits related to the generation of strength, depends on the type of program and the care with the prescription of the muscular actions, the intensity, the volume, the selection and order of the exercises, the rest periods between the series and the frequency.

1. MUSCULAR ACTIONS

Regarding the muscular actions, in the resistance training, there is the inclusion of concentric, eccentric and isometric actions. In the eccentric actions, there is a greater development of the force in comparison with the concentric and isometric actions, besides being beneficial for the hypertrophy, generating more pronounced late muscular pain. The concentric actions promote an improvement in the force gain when associated with the eccentric actions. Moreover, finally, isometric exercises can also provide benefits for the subject, as in functional isometry. However, these exercises have a secondary character in resistance training.

2. CHARGE

For resistance training, with changes in training loads, there are changes in metabolism, hormones, neural and cardiovascular, from acute responses in the exercise. RATAMESS et al. (2009) proposed a scheme to determine the appropriate load, according to the needs and limitations of the subject: 1) the increase of the load occurs according to the percentage of 1 RM of the subject; 2) the increase of the absolute load is based on the numbers of repetitions proposed in the training session, or 3) the increase of the load must be within the prescription zone.

This scheme allows the determination of the load associated to the training level of the subject, since for the untrained the load must be lower, between 45-50% of 1 RM, or when the subject is moderately trained, and repetition is prescribed between 15 to 25, the proposed loads should also be light. However, as

training progresses and the subject level improves, an increase in load becomes necessary, with a load of at least 80% of 1 RM being adequate, generating new neural and force adaptations. Some researches in resistance training have demonstrated that the variation of the load and the training intensity during the periodization of the subject is necessary, since, in a meta-analysis of data, it was observed that loads equivalent to 60% of 1 RM, is more adequate for untrained subjects, loads corresponding to 80% of 1 RM produce more significant effects on increased strength in trained subjects and 85% of 1 RM is more effective in athletes. The use of 50-60% of 1 RM for untrained subjects is necessary, initially, as a way of facilitating the learning of the appropriate training technique, (RATAMESS et al., 2009). The load can be altered with the increase or decrease of the repetitions proposed for the exercise, for example, there are several studies pointing out that the training with repetitions between 1-6 RM would be the most propitious for the generation and increase of the maximum strength of the subject, although, for an even greater increase in strength, it is necessary to perform 3-5 RM when compared to training corresponding to 9-11 and 20-28 RM. Therefore, loads and intensity should be prescribed above a threshold, based on the number of target repetitions, for improved efficacy of progression and gain of muscle strength.

3. VOLUME

As RATAMESS et al. (2009), the training volume can be described as being a sum of the total number of repetitions, multiplied by the load (Kg) used, resulting in the duration of action of the active muscles during exercise. Correct determination of training volume is important as it produces neural, hypertrophic, metabolic, and hormonal adaptations.

Control of this training volume can be done by the number of exercises performed during the session, the number of repetitions per set, or the number of sets of exercises. For example, training sessions with low volume, high load, low repetitions, moderate to a high number of sets were considered as a characteristic program of resistance training.

4. ORDER OF THE EXERCISES AND INTERVAL

The order of the exercises considerably affects the performance of acute muscle strength, for example when opposing exercises (antagonistic movements), having their strength reduced when performed consecutively. Another example is multi-articular exercises (supine, squatting, leg press), because when they are performed after the activated muscle group has undergone stress due to several exercises already performed, it may present a decline in performance. However, because multi-joint exercises favour the gain of strength, one can potentiate their performance when performed at the beginning of a workout. Another important aspect would be the amount of rest between the series, since this affects the individual's metabolic, hormonal and cardiovascular responses significantly, as well as compromising performance after acute stress of this individual.

5. PHYSIOLOGICAL ADAPTATIONS

Taking into account the fact that physical exercise in general, according to BRUM et al. (2004), it is a situation that removes the body from its homeostasis, due to the increased energy demand of the activated muscle group and of the organism as a whole, which is why it takes several physiological adaptations to supply this increase of the metabolic demand, as per adaptations in cardiovascular function during exercise. In relation to static or isometric exercises, an increase in heart rate occurs,

with maintenance of systolic volume and a small increase in cardiac output (amount of blood pumped by the left ventricle per minute for the arteries), as well as increases in peripheral vascular resistance (opposition of blood vessels, which may be more or less contracted or dilated, to blood circulation) that results in an exacerbated elevation of blood pressure; This is due to the contraction of the muscles maintained during isometric contraction, obstructing the muscular blood flow, then metabolites produced during the contraction begin to accumulate, activating muscular chemoreceptors, which generate an increase in the sympathetic nervous activity (stimulates actions that mobilize energy, such as response to a stressor event, such as acceleration of heart rate, increase in blood pressure, blood sugar concentration and activation of metabolism in general, since the postganglionic neurons of the sympathetic nervous system mainly secrete noradrenaline). In contrast, dynamic or isotonic exercises do not obstruct blood flow, since its contraction is followed by joint movements; but there is also an increase in the sympathetic nervous activity, triggered by the activation of the central command, FORJAZ & TINUCCI (2000) apud BRUM et al. (2004). As a result of this increase in sympathetic activity, increased heart rate, systolic volume and cardiac output, as well as vasodilation in the activated musculature, occur through the production of muscle metabolites and reduction of peripheral vascular resistance.

Based on this analysis, that both static and dynamic exercises exert significant influence, mainly in the sympathetic nervous activity, triggering several other physiological changes, it is seen that the resisted exercises play a prominent role, because according to FORJAZ et al. (2003), they produce both a dynamic contraction as well as isometric contraction during its realization.

Regarding the chronic adaptations, some studies show that the heart rate of trained individuals was lower than in untrained individuals. About the blood pressure of individuals who undergo resistance training, it was demonstrated in a study by Fleck (1988) apud POLITO & FARINATTI (2003) that they present values of resting blood pressure on average or slightly below average compared to the sedentary population.

6.HORMONAL ADAPTATIONS

Hormones also act in the nervous system, with the elaboration and effectuation of the responses to certain external events. For a better understanding, CANALI & KRUEL (2001) conceptualize the hormones as being a chemical substance, secreted by specialized cells or endocrine glands to the sage or the organ, generating physiological responses in other specific cells, that is, the hormones are considered physiological regulators, secreted only by endocrine glands.

In the study carried out by CANALI & FRUEL (2001), hormones are considered to be modified amino acids, or small peptides, polypeptides or even simple or conjugated proteins and their action in the body occurs through a relationship between more than one hormone, be cooperative or antagonistic. To regulate the release of the hormones, the body has two mechanisms, the most common negative feedback, also considered as negative feedback, where hormone A, considered a stimulant of the production of hormone B, is inhibited at the moment when the concentration of B is high (BERNE & LEVY, 1996). The other mechanism used, however, considered a less common mechanism, is positive feedback, which recognizes hormone A to potentiate the biological effect of hormone B, increasing its secretion (BERNE & LEVY, 1996). In addition to these mechanisms,

hormone secretion can also be regulated through neural control, increasing or decreasing it depending on external or internal stimuli.

Also, CANALI & KRUEL (2001) point out that one of the external stimuli that influence the production or inhibition of some hormones is the practice of physical exercises. Therefore, CANALI & KRUEL suggest that physical exercise influences some alterations in hormonal secretion, as for example in the case of growth hormone, also known as GH, whose main functions are increased amino acid uptake and protein synthesis; potentiates the use of lipids and reduces the use of glucose in obtaining energy; stimulates cell reproduction and growth of cartilage and bone; and with the exercise the production of this hormone is stimulated in the same proportion in which the intensity of the exercise also increases. Another hormone that changes with exercise is the stimulating thyroid hormone (TSH), whose function is to increase the individual's metabolism (GUYTON & HALL, 1997) and with exercise the release of this hormone is also stimulated. Exercise also stimulates the production of the hormone called adrenocorticotropin (ACTH), whose function is to regulate the growth and secretion of the adrenal cortex, responsible for the secretion of cortisol. The follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) promotes the growth of the follicles and in men stimulates the development of spermatozoa, and in women it stimulates the production of estrogen (low rates); besides FSH, another hormone known as luteinizing (LH), promotes the secretion of estrogen and progesterone, having an essential function in the menstrual cycle. These two hormones, FSH and LH, do not present a consistent theoretical basis about their changes in physical exercise, due to their natural production through endogenous pulsation (LH is released in intervals of 90 to 110 minutes), besides the fact their concentrations are produced or decreased under the influence of anxiety. So there is a difficulty in differentiating the production of these hormones from the physical exercise of their natural production.

Another hormone stimulated by physical exercise is prolactin (PRL), whose function is to develop breasts and milk production, without the need for any stimulus, however, with exercise, PRL levels increase (CANALI & KRUEL, 2001). Vasopressin, also known as antidiuretic hormone (ADH), whose primary function is to maintain body water levels in addition to regulating body fluids. Because of this function that ADH has, the practice of physical exercise exerts significant influence, dramatically increasing its production, to maintain body fluids during practice, especially on very hot days. Regarding the adrenal or adrenal glands located on the kidneys, it is worth mentioning the influences of physical exercise under the catecholamines, epinephrine (or adrenaline) and norepinephrine (or noradrenaline), which also suffer alterations in their release with the practice of physical exercises, having their levels increased. Mineralocorticoids are also hormones produced by the adrenal glands, with aldosterone being the most important. With physical exercise aldosterone levels increase progressively, as the body's way of maintaining body fluids and homeostasis (regulating body temperature). Consideration should also be given to the importance of the hormone cortisol.

7.RESISTANCE TRAINING AND DEPRESSION

Some studies in the USA suggest that the controlled and organized practice of physical exercise offers a reduction in the symptoms of depression and anxiety for the general population (MELLO et al., 2005).

In today's society, we see the need of the individual to enter

into an active lifestyle, from the regular practice of physical exercises, since with the technological development, coming from the industrial revolution and the technological revolution, stress levels, anxiety and sedentary lifestyle are considered high, damaging the individual's well-being and health (ANTUNES et al., 2006). That is why there is an increase in the general interest for the practice of physical exercises with the goal of achieving physical and cognitive well-being.

ANTUNES et al. (2006) suggest that individuals who exercise regularly are less likely to develop mental disorders compared to sedentary individuals, stating that physical exercise helps physical and psychological health. According to GUTIN (1973) apud ANTUNES et al. (2006) suggests that short-term exercise, maintaining a heart rate between 90 and 120 beats per minute (BPM) has benefits for the individual's cognitive function, in other words, resistance training may present real benefits in depressive individuals, since, based on the studies of RATAMESS et al. (2009), training sessions with low volume, high load, low repetitions, for example, are considered as resistance training. These benefits generated by resistance training are related to the increase in levels of neurotransmitters and changes in brain structures, since physical exercise promotes an increase in cerebral blood flow and oxygen and energetic substrates, guaranteeing improvements in the individual's cognitive function. However, these gains become effective when the exercise is practised in the long term (ANTUNES et al., 2006). In this way, ANTUNES et al. (2006) suggest that training, in addition to increasing levels of neurotransmitters, also increases the concentrations of the hormones norepinephrine and its precursors (noradrenaline, adrenaline), serotonin and β -endorphin, in other words, ANTUNES et al. refer to "neuroendocrine and humoral changes promoted by exercises, such as increased adrenaline, noradrenaline, ACTH, vasopressin and β -endorphin."

Then, starting from the studies found, it is known that the depressive individual undergoes several hormonal, physiological, neural, and cognitive alterations, in short, depression causes a certain imbalance in the individual's organism. Moreover, resistance training, in turn, presents benefits to the body of the individual, such as hormonal adaptations, establishing a balance and maintenance in the concentrations of various hormones; or even generating an improvement in the cognitive function of the depressive individual, because, as has been seen previously, in the face of a stressor event, the response organized by the organism depends on how the individual considers this event and can be relevant, pleasant and terrifying, the organism determines the appropriate response (MARGIS et al., 2003). Thus, with resistance training, the individual has faster cognitive processing, since physical exercise influences the processes that control the preparation of the response, when the individual is in a stressful event (WRISBERG & HERBERT, 1976 apud ANTUNES et al.

CONSIDERATIONS

The present study shows that the association between resistance training and the treatment of individuals with depression can promote benefits both in hormonal and cognitive function, which would characterize an improvement in the ability of the depressed individual to determine the degree of dangerousness of a particular stressor event, and then predict and choose, with more speed and self-confidence, the appropriate response. It is also worth mentioning that, through this bibliographic survey, depression begins to cause concern in today's society, since it is in increasing development, with no age or gender limit, and

is considered a severe public health problem. This is due to the fact that individuals are less and less active, that is, sedentary, due to the technological advance, since society demands of the individual speed, competence, perfection and productivity, where moments of pleasure and rest are seen with bad eyes, already that if the individual is stopped, it means that he is not producing.

Therefore, the excess of demands and demands on the part of the present society, the sedentarism and the lack of adhesion in physical trainings, generates an enormous pressure in the individual, causing anxiety, that in turn causes the individual to feel fear (or even fear) in not being able to be accepted in society or fail to face the challenges imposed, then there is a certain withdrawal, lack of will to try to solve problems, feelings of inferiority and lack of pleasure in performing daily activities. Moreover, then, through resistance training, the individual begins to have an improvement in their self-esteem, self-control and consequently, feel safer to perform their tasks and society. Besides stimulating the production of hormones favourable to the control of anxiety, stress and pleasure.

COMPETING INTERESTS

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